

CRIMINOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THEFT FROM RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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Abstract. The article analyzes the criminological characteristics of thefts committed from residential premises and substantiates the practical necessity for operational officers to be aware of this aspect.

Keywords: characteristics, theft, residential building, crime prevention, cause, conditions, stages of committing a crime.

The criminological characteristics of theft from residential buildings refer to a set of criminological data about individuals who have committed crimes, which can be used in preventing, studying the causes and conditions of this crime, and combating it.

In criminology, categories such as "cause," "circumstance," "criminal," and "criminal personality" that contribute to criminal events are studied [1]. The concept of "criminal personality" specifically expresses the social characteristics of the offender, serving to reveal the individual's "social profile" [2].

Prevention and detection of theft from residential premises has always been an important task in the republic, as from 1991 to 2022, a total of 74,228 crimes were committed in the criminal investigation sphere. However, it was observed that 1/3 of these crimes, or 35% (25,600), were theft crimes, and 62% (15,872) of these theft crimes were committed from residential premises.

To prevent and detect theft from residential premises, it is necessary to study information about the causes and conditions that enabled the commission of this crime [3].

The reason that enabled the commission of theft from residential premises is a process related to the social status of the person (or persons) who committed this crime.

The main reasons for theft from residential premises are:

firstly, not all able-bodied citizens have a productive occupation [4];

secondly, the income source of some working citizens is insufficient for their personal needs [5];

thirdly, some citizens (mainly those with previous convictions) are unwilling to engage in socially beneficial work and desire to acquire wealth through any easy means;

fourthly, certain perpetrators of residential theft are not identified and thus not held criminally liable (this leads to the repeated commission of this crime by the same individuals) [6].

The main conditions contributing to the commission of theft from residential premises include:

negligence or indifference of citizens in the use of their property;

failure to take the necessary security measures to strengthen the storage of property of individuals and legal entities;

insufficient supervision by internal affairs officers of persons previously convicted, addicted to the use of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, alcoholic beverages, temporarily unemployed or raised in an unhealthy family;

leaving some young people unattended or not engaged in socially useful work;

incomplete assignment of forces and resources of internal affairs bodies to territories where crimes have occurred;

Insufficient organization of operational-search and preventive measures [7];

Systematic non-establishment of cooperation between the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies, as well as other state bodies, khokimiyats, enterprises, institutions and organizations, public structures in the prevention of theft (for example, in the area of night lighting, installation of surveillance cameras, etc.).

When analyzing statistical data for 2022-2024 for the republic, the following information was revealed about 1,234 persons who committed theft crimes:

According to the sex of the perpetrator: the majority of these crimes (79%) were committed by men, while the remainder were committed by women (21%). This is because women's criminal behavior differs from men's in terms of the scale and nature of crimes, methods and tools used to commit them, and the selection of victims. Family, domestic, and other similar circumstances influence the residential theft crimes committed by women. In such cases, residential thefts by women are often committed not out of necessity, but by those who steal whatever they can get their hands on.

By age: 11.8% of criminals were minors, 38.6% were persons aged 18-30, and 49.6% were persons aged 31-60. Individuals aged 18-30 are those whose anti-social orientation is clearly manifested. The next age group - residential thefts committed by persons aged 30-60 years - are characterized by extremely high professionalism. These residential theft crimes are carefully planned and prepared. As a result, homeowners suffer significant damage, and the perpetrators are rarely exposed and punished for committing the crime.

According to social status: 22.1% were previously convicted. When analyzing a total of 13,950 residential theft crimes committed in the republic from 2016 to 2022, the following data was revealed: Out of 2,800 residential thefts committed by previously convicted persons, 910 (32.5%) occurred in Fergana region, 304 (12.1%) in Tashkent city, and 270 (9.6%) in Bukhara region. Of 1,500 residential thefts committed by minors, 240 (16%) occurred in Fergana region, 330 (22%) in Samarkand, and 130 (8.6%) in Andijan regions. 930 residential thefts were committed by unemployed and uneducated persons, of which 320 (34.4%) occurred in Fergana region and another 320 (34.4%) in Tashkent city. Out of 1,140 residential thefts committed while intoxicated, 310 (27.1%) occurred in Tashkent city and 140 (12.2%) in Fergana region. Of 4,880 residential thefts committed by young people, 1,190 (24.3%) occurred in Fergana region, 680 (13.9%) in Tashkent, and 630 (12.9%) in Samarkand regions. Out of 2,700 residential thefts committed by women, 670 (24.8%) occurred in Fergana region, 280 (10.3%) in Namangan region, and 300 (11.1%) in Andijan region.

In general, analysis of persons who committed theft from a dwelling shows that more than half of theft crimes committed from a dwelling in the territory of the republic, or 54.2% (152), are committed by previously convicted persons, 46.6% (70%) are committed by minors; 3/2 or 68.8% (64) were unemployed and uneducated,

39.3% (45) - while intoxicated; more than half of thefts committed from residential premises, or 51.1% (250) - by young people; 46.2% (125 cases) are committed by women. The largest number of such thefts occurred in the cities of Fergana and Tashkent.

7.3% of burglaries committed from residential premises were committed by temporarily unemployed individuals (including 25% by citizens with low legal awareness and culture). In this case, a correlation is observed between the level of education of the guilty party and criminal behavior; 21 percent - citizens living and working in the same neighborhood as the victims, or close acquaintances (son-in-law, nephew, classmate, etc.).

This is because knowing information about the victim (the victim's living conditions, where their property is located, when they are in the house, the possibility of entering and exiting the dwelling, and other similar information) facilitates the commission of theft from a dwelling. A special aspect of this situation is that if these persons commit theft from a dwelling, in most cases, property belonging to the victims is stolen directly from their place of residence, no changes are observed in the house, and as a result, the victims do not notice the thefts committed in their house for several days, which leads to late notification to the Internal Affairs Department and some problems in solving the crime. As a result of the study, 12% of thefts committed in residential premises were committed by persons from other regions. It has been observed that such crimes were committed as a result of coming from other regions in search of work or specifically for the purpose of committing a crime. In such cases, problems were observed in solving crimes due to the fact that they came from other regions, committed crimes, tried to hide from the scene, and transferred stolen evidence to other regions. However, during the study, we can also observe that 72.3% of thefts committed from residential premises in other regions were committed by persons previously convicted of committing similar crimes. Therefore, it is necessary to establish prompt cooperation in this direction with the employees of the Department of Internal Affairs of neighboring cities, districts, and regions.

When analyzing the circumstances and time of theft from residential premises, the following were revealed:

Committed in complicity or by an individual: 12 percent - in complicity (2-3 or more persons jointly), 88 percent - individually. Because we can observe that most individual thefts were committed by previously convicted persons and recidivist criminals or by citizens living and working in the same neighborhood as the victims, or by close acquaintances (groom, daughter-in-law, nephew, classmate, relatives, etc.);

44.7% (624 cases) were committed at night (from 6:00 PM to 8:00 AM), 33.3% (465 cases) were committed during the day (from 8:00 AM to 6:00 PM), and the remaining 21.9% (306 cases) were committed at unknown times. The main reason for their frequent occurrence at night is the insufficient attention paid to property protection, as well as the perpetrator's desire to avoid the possibility of exposure in the commission of the crime, which is explained by the possibility of committing the crime more covertly in order to evade responsibility; information on the analysis of crimes committed during the day does not allow for the identification of any patterns, but creates a basis for the development of preventive measures; (Most burglaries from residential premises were observed between 10:00 and 12:00 during the day and between 22:00 and 24:00 at night. Because during the day, the homeowners may not be home at this time, and at night, the homeowners may not be home or

may be asleep. At the same time, most of the thefts were committed from residential premises.)

by days of the week: 15.5% - Monday; 13.3% - Tuesday; 13.9% - Wednesday; 13.3% - Thursday; 16.1% - Friday; 12.5% - Saturday; 10.5% - on Sundays. From this, we can observe that theft from a residential premise is more often committed at the beginning and end of the week, that is, on working days (Mondays and Fridays);

By seasons: 27.3% (382) - in autumn (8.5% or 118 - in September, 10% or 140 - in October, 8.9% or 124 - in November); 23.8% (333) - in winter (9.1% or 127 - in December, 8.3% or 116 - in January, 6.5% or 90 - in February); 19.4% (271) - in spring (6.9% or 96 - in March, 6.7% or 94 - in April, 5.8% or 81 - in May); 25.1% (351) - in summer (6.8% or 95 - in June, 9.4% or 131 - in July, 9.0% or 125 - in August). From this, we can observe that thefts from residential premises are most often committed during the summer and autumn seasons or in July, October, November, and December.

From the empirical materials we studied, it became clear that the majority of housing theft crimes currently occur without prior preparation (74.6%). Criminals usually do not pre-examine the object, do not prepare special weapons for theft in advance, they also know nothing about the property available in the dwelling, but are ready to enter any dwelling in the absence of homeowners and in conditions of easy access to the dwelling.

Particular attention should be paid to the fact that almost 15 percent of burglaries committed from residential premises are committed by a group of individuals.

In most cases, this group consists of two to three people and is usually formed in the place where criminals work and live. A characteristic feature of modern residential theft is the lack of choice among thieves. They steal various items, namely money, household appliances, clothing, food products, and many other things. However, thieves often steal small items that are easy to transfer (sell) or can be profitable and used for their own needs.

In this regard, items of criminal encroachment that are valuable to thieves are of particular importance. Among them, the most common are: money, including foreign currency (29.3%); jewelry (38.8%); household appliances, television, video and audio equipment (27.4%); computers, office and other office equipment (12.6%); communication devices (31.1%).

At the same time, to increase the effectiveness of the fight against theft from residential premises, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of theft. Firstly, in almost 72% of thefts from residential and other premises, criminals carry out theft in the territory of various cities and districts where the theft occurred. Secondly, the main part of the trafficking of stolen items occurs in the first three days after the theft, including more than 80% on the first day. Thirdly, the transfer of stolen goods has a number of patterns related to local characteristics and the operational situation in cities. The transfer of stolen goods is not unsystematic, but, for example, is "connected" with various trade objects, which in most cases include commodity and food markets, peculiar "barakholkas," and spontaneously emerging markets where the sale and purchase of used goods are carried out.

Analysis of thefts from residential premises committed on the territory of the republic shows that stolen material evidence is transferred mainly to random persons in various markets, as well as to persons engaged in the purchase and sale of used items and objects. A certain portion of stolen items, such as foreign currency, jewelry, or communication devices (mobile phones), are traded in special "black" markets that arise near large retail outlets.

Currently, stolen items are sold to: relatives of the criminal - 16.6%; acquaintances of the criminal - 32.4%; employees of trade and public catering - 15.2%; random persons - 14.6%; persons engaged in the purchase and sale of used items (including communication devices, jewelry, household appliances, etc.) - 21.2%.

In modern conditions, completely new methods of transferring stolen items are emerging. Here we are talking about the transfer of stolen items using Internet capabilities. As is known, in the Internet environment, there are numerous websites (for example, the Olx.uz website) that place private announcements about the purchase and sale of certain items, as well as the provision of services for their purchase and sale. At the same time, the complete anonymity of the persons posting such announcements on the Internet is ensured. Not through direct contact to the agreement on the purchase or sale of certain items. Rather, it is achieved through Internet correspondence or negotiations on the phone indicated in the announcement. All this makes it much easier to sell stolen items, since now the criminal no longer needs to carry stolen items in markets (or other places) looking for buyers. It is sufficient to place an announcement about the sale of a certain item or to use an announcement about the purchase of such an item. In this case, the probability of being caught while transferring the stolen item is minimal.

Stages of committing theft from residential premises:

stage of preparation for the commission of a crime;

stage of the commission of the criminal act;

stage of temporary storage, use, disposal of stolen property.

In the first stage, the selection of the object of theft is carried out; visiting the object and studying its direction, protection of the object, lighting; determining the number of selected participants in the commission of the crime and distributing their duties; preparing the necessary objects and means for committing theft and other actions are carried out.

In the second stage, the object of theft is visited on a planned basis, and the criminal act is carried out. At the stage of carrying out a criminal act, the organizer is considered the main figure, such a person is usually previously convicted of malicious crimes, first draws attention to the participants of the group in order to see who will benefit him, studies their abilities, and equally distributes their duties. The organizer tries to find individuals with experience in selecting group members.

When committing theft from residential premises, certain participants in the crime consume alcoholic beverages. The reason is that a person who has consumed alcohol tries to overcome some fear and emotions, and this helps to commit a crime.

In the third stage, the person who committed theft from the dwelling takes measures to permanently or temporarily store, use, and transfer the stolen property, that is, to sell it. In conclusion, the operative officer's knowledge of the criminological characteristics of the crime of theft committed from residential premises, organizing official activities based on analysis, serves to make a forecast (forecast) for the early prevention of this crime in the future.

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